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Submission of comments on ‘the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation’

Public Consultation from the European Commission

Comments from:

Name of organisation or individual

Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy, Dr Pin Lean Lau, Dr Mathieu Guerriaud, Dr Phoebe Li, Dr Éloïse Gennet, Dr Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag, and Prof Christian Chabannon on behalf of the EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw and the I-BioLex research project

Please find below the answer to the public consultation on ‘the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation’ by **Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy** (*CNRS Permanent researcher in law, UMR 7318 International, Comparative and European laws-DICE CERIC, Aix Marseille University, Toulon University, Pau & Pays de l’Adour University, Aix-en-Provence, France*), **Dr Pin Lean Lau** (*Lecturer in Bio-Law and Researcher at the Centre for Artificial Intelligence: Social & Digital Innovations, Brunel Law School, Brunel University London, United Kingdom*), **Dr Mathieu Guerriaud** (*Maître de conférences en sciences pharmaceutiques, Centre de recherches sur le droit des investissements et des marchés internationaux, CREDIMI, Université de Bourgogne, Dijon, France*), **Dr Phoebe Li** (*Senior Lecturer in Law, University of Sussex, United Kingdom*), **Dr Éloïse Gennet** (*Post-doctoral researcher in law, UMR 7318 International, Comparative and European laws-DICE CERIC, Aix Marseille University, Toulon University, Pau & Pays de l’Adour University, Aix-en-Provence, France*), **Dr Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag** (*Directrice de Recherche INSERM, CERPOP UMR 1295, Inserm, Université de Toulouse - Université Paul Sabatier -Toulouse III, Toulouse, France*), and **Prof Christian Chabannon** (*Biotherapies, Marseille Research Centre in Cancerology, Director of*

the Cell Therapy Centre at Paoli-Calmettes Institute (IPC), Coordinator-doctor at CIC Biothérapies Inserm CBT-1409 –AMU –AP-HM -IPC) on behalf of the Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw from the European Association of Health Law (EAHL) and the I-BioLex research project.

The EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw is co-chaired by Aurélie Mahalatchimy (UMR 7318 DICE CERIC, CNRS, Aix Marseille University, France) and Mark Flear (Queen’s University Belfast, UK) and involved legal experts in Supranational Biolaw, mainly academics, from 14 EU member States, the UK and Switzerland.

The [EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw](#) has been created in 2020 within the European Association of Health Law. It aims to promote European health law, especially in its European-level dimension, regarding the law and the various legal issues arising from technological advances related to medicine and biotechnology. Among its activities, it mobilises its members to address demands from several groups within society, including legislators and regulators, scientists (researchers and clinicians), and patients regarding Supranational Biolaw. The EAHL IG on Supranational Biolaw is also the leader of one of the 2021 Thematic Network of the European Union Health Policy Platform. The Thematic Network is entitled “Health as a fundamental value. Towards an equitable and inclusive pharmaceutical strategy for the EU”. On the basis of webinars and online discussions on the EU Health Policy Platform, it is aimed to produce a Joint Statement to be endorsed as widely as possible. This Joint Statement that will be released in April 2022 on the EU Health Policy Platform will also be particularly relevant in the context of the revision of the pharmaceutical legislation.

Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy, Dr Pin Lean Lau, Dr Mathieu Guerriaud, Dr Phoebe Li, Dr Éloïse Gennet and Dr Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag provides this answer on behalf of the EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw.

The I-BioLex project “Fragmentation and defragmentation of the law on biomedical innovations” is funded by the French National Agency for Research (ANR-20-CE26-0007-01, coord. A. Mahalatchimy; 2021-2024). [I-BioLex](#) is exploring whether the processes of fragmentation (division or segmentation), and defragmentation (gathering together, connecting or ‘harmonising’) can jointly contribute to and express the adaptability and coherence of the law as it pertains to Biomedical innovations (BI), in areas such as gene therapy, regenerative medicine, or nanomedicine. Building on the works linked to legal oversight of complex BI, law temporality and law fragmentation phenomenon, I-BioLex uses comparative and interdisciplinary approaches and combines theoretical and empirical elements to test this hypothesis while helping to determine how the law on BI can serve diverse societal objectives. Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy, Dr Éloïse Gennet, Dr Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag and Prof Christian Chabannon provides this answer on behalf of the I-BioLex Research project.

Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy, Dr Pin Lean Lau, Dr Mathieu Guerriaud, Dr Phoebe Li, Dr Éloïse Gennet, Dr Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag, and Prof Christian Chabannon are grateful to the European Commission to have been given the opportunity to contribute to this consultation.

Please see below our complete answer.

Q1 In your opinion, are there any other issues that should be addressed in this revision?

This revision should also address the following issues:

- The new legislation should be based on both articles 114 and 168§4 c) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. Therefore, the pharmaceutical legislation should be more balanced in its objectives, especially in taking into account the achievement of public health objectives through patients' access to medicines wider, i.e. including those which are not following the standard marketing authorisation pathway or manufactured at the industrial scale.
- The specificities of the rules applicable to different kinds of biological medicinal products should be clarified: e.g. current dispersion within the EU legislation, potential overlapping between medicinal products based on recombinant DNA technology and immunological medicinal products.
- The development and need of regulatory support for more coordination at the EU level for bioproduction regarding biotherapies (biological medicinal products in general, and more specifically Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products) and health data's registries regarding real-world evidence should be taken into account.
- The cumulative implementation of several legislations should be considered: e.g. Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products and Orphan medicinal products regulations, Genetically Modified Organisms and medicines legislations, medical devices and medicines legislations.

Q2 How has the legislation performed in terms of the following elements?

The following aspects need to be strengthened: Prevention of misuse, and Proper actions to identify providers of unproven therapies and help users to unequivocally differentiate between true innovations and unproven therapies (patients and relatives education).

Q3 How important are the following elements for defining 'unmet medical needs'?

For 5: It is important to clearly delineate where the wording "Innovative" applies: the technology used to manufacture the drug? The biological or physiological phenomenon targeted by the drug? The indication that is being treated? If we think of ATMPs, the confusion between "innovative process used to manufacture" and "innovative indication / biological mechanism" may explain a significant fraction of commercial failures in the early years after publication of the EU Regulation.

For 1: "seriousness" of a disease should no longer be exclusively considered in terms of overall survival, but also in terms of Quality of Life (QoL), including being free of the disease but also of treatment complications. Interviewing patients and patients' advocates is key to fully understand patients' demands that do not fully overlap with HCPs' views.

For all: These elements have to be considered together. For instance, the seriousness of a disease (1) becomes less important if it already exists a satisfactory and accessible treatment for this disease.

For 2 and 4: “authorized treatment” should be considered widely as encompassing treatment authorized through marketing authorization or other expediting access schemes such as compassionate use (Article 83 Regulation (EC) n°726/2004) or ‘named patients’ exception (Article 5§1 Directive 2001/83/EC). If “authorized treatment” is considered as including marketing authorization pathway only, elements 2 and 4 become less important if it exists satisfactory treatments accessible through expediting access schemes.

Q4 What do you think of the following measures to support innovation, including for ‘unmet medical needs’?

Yes, definition of “unmet needs” must be improved. It is barely acceptable that a treatment that definitely corrects the biological mechanism that underpins the disease phenotype in an inherited disorder falls in the same category as the small fraction of patients who unfortunately are resistant or refractory to standard of care in an otherwise usually curable ailment.

Q5 Should there be specific regulatory incentives for the development of new antimicrobials while taking into account the need for more prudent use and if so what should they be?

Yes, because overprescribing, overuse and inappropriate use of antibiotics will not be controlled exclusively at the EU level and in the field of medicine. These problems will be imported from other countries and continents, fueled by international exchanges, by inequalities in healthcare system that prevail in many countries outside of Europe, by practices in fields other than medicine (i.e. agricultural practices as an example), and thus we will not be able to fully escape these issues.

The development of new antimicrobials (AM) has been slow due to a variety of reasons, including but not limited to regulatory barriers and profitability challenges – regulatory incentives should be explored (whilst maintaining key principles for prudent AM use, stewardship, national programs of implementation and oversight, surveillance, etc). It is also vital to ensure access to affordable drugs in Low-to-Middle-Income Countries and for the prices of new AM to be kept generally low. There are existing regulatory incentives from various jurisdictions around the globe – and a hybrid model which incorporates both push (decreasing costs) and pull (increase market revenue for newly approved AM) mechanisms could be workable as either push or pull incentives alone are inadequate. There are two examples currently being trialled for regulatory incentives. One is the UK’s pilot project for regulatory incentives – it uses a hybrid subscription model to reimburse pharma companies for AM drug development. It combines a value-based reimbursement with a fully delinked Market Entry Reward (MER), with AM being subjected to health technology assessment that is conducted by the appropriate regulatory body. Suppliers/manufacturers which pass this technology assessment will be reimbursed on the basis of a multi-year contract paid in yearly installments, with the antibiotics’ performance over time affecting the actual annual fee paid to suppliers. Sweden has a similar model, with a slight difference: the Swedish pilot has a partially-delinked MER, participating suppliers are able to perform volume-based sales while also being guaranteed a minimum annual revenue for qualifying AM. These are apparently quite novel

ways of approaching the question of incentivizing new AM drug development, and could be explored further.

(See Dutescu I A, Hillier S A. Encouraging the development of new antibiotics: are financial incentives the right way forward? A systematic review and case study. *Infection and Drug Resistance* (Dove Press) 2021) relied on Renwick's framework for selecting an incentive model for new AM (see Renwick M, Brogan DM, Mossialos E. A systematic review and critical assessment of incentive strategies for discovery and development of novel antibiotics. *J Antibiot* (Tokyo) 2016).

Q6 How would you assess the following measures to create an adapted, agile and predictable regulatory framework for novel products?

For 4 "Create adaptive regulatory frameworks": This paradigmatic situation where two regulatory frameworks co-exist for the manufacturing and administration of therapies that share many aspects in their nature and mechanism of actions must be resolved. It questions the binary where manufacturing AND administration are under stringent separated responsibilities.

Q7. Do you think that certain definitions and the scope of the legislation need to be updated to reflect scientific and technological developments in the sector (e.g. personalised medicines, bedside manufacturing, artificial intelligence) and if so what would you propose to change?

On the necessary updates:

- Updates on the uses of new tools, such as AI, in pharmaceutical activities. Attention should be paid to ensure the coherent interplay between upcoming pharmaceutical & AI legislations. The latter are not fully dedicated to health matters and should be adapted to: 1/drug discovery activities and, 2/ quality and security of drug development, distribution and commercialisation. Some key elements should drive the thoughts in this regards such as: human oversight, respect of fundamental rights (information, transparency), non-discrimination and respect for the public interest.
- Updates on the finalities, such as personalised medicine. Personalized medicine challenges the traditional model of mass-manufacturing for conventional drugs. Even though vague, this concept implies that the new tools to be developed in the future will be more tailored to patients' needs and that drugs will adapt to the biological response of groups of individuals or a single individual. Pathways towards this objective should be better identified as well as issues for the various actors (industry, academia, medical professionals and patients). Connections with the CTR, GDPR, IVDR are key elements to ensure coherence towards PM.
- For AI and PM, particular attention should be paid to human oversight, adequate information, transparency, public interest, but also to non-discrimination and fair/equitable representation (e.g. in gender, race, age...) to avoid algorithmic biases. The updates, for example incorporating AI in PM, must be careful to ensure that algorithmic bias can be minimized as much as possible. The most common algorithm biases in healthcare relate to race and gender inequities. Updates in legislation should reflect the importance of ensuring representative, clean and fair data sets, especially if

data sets are to be used to train other ML algorithms. For example, whilst the EU Draft Regs on AI requires data sets to be tested, validated, etc, it is unclear how AI systems will be tested for bias: whether the benchmark will be equality in opportunity, or equality in outcomes. Care should be taken, in that facilitating progress towards individually tailored interventions in PM should work in complementarity with AI, and not at odds. Whilst there may be a need to cluster identity groupings in AI algorithms as a means to avoid or minimize algorithmic bias especially at the intersectionality of multiple social groups (e.g. pregnant women, women in menopause, women of color, etc) this should be done in a way that advances gender equality in AI healthcare, whilst retaining the promise and goals of PM.

- Frameworks – both regulatory and in view of financial incentives – should be better adapted. Nevertheless, attention should be paid to Pharms which may have taken advantage of this perception to further introduce alternative pricing models where the price reflects savings for NOT using SOC or supportive care, rather than the actual costs of development and manufacturing.

On the definitions:

- Focus the definition of medicinal products (MPs) on processes (e.g. physico-chemical-biological testing) rather than on the source.
- Need to harmonize the European definition of gene therapy MPs with the ICH one. The European definition is quite different from the American definition, both of which are different from the definition that the ICH seems to propose. A harmonization of the definitions would be desirable to improve access to the market for these products by facilitating the submission of marketing authorisation applications.
- The definition of immunological medicinal products is old and no longer really reflects reality. In addition, the examples given in the definition of vaccine are all vaccines against infectious pathologies, whereas therapeutic vaccines against cancer are emerging. There is a need for clarification in this field (in particular, there is a risk of overlap between the definition of vaccines (not against infectious diseases) and the definitions of ATMPs (both GTMPs and CTMPs).
- The definition of medicinal products developed by means of one of certain biotechnological processes no longer really reflects reality. There is a risk of overlaps both with ATMPs and immunological medicinal products.

Q8 How would you assess the following measures to improve patient access to medicines across the EU?

To resolve this problem payment and reimbursement negotiations should not be left to national Health Technology Assessment (HTA) agencies exclusively, and should be included in the pre-MA negotiations, based on a priori hypotheses on efficacy/risk ratio for the targeted disease(s).

Q9 In your view, to what extent would the following measures support access to affordable medicines?

Q10 What measures could stimulate the repurposing of off-patent medicines and provide additional uses of the medicine against new diseases and medical conditions? Please justify your answers.

The similarities between repurposing and development of generic / biosimilar drugs could be explored.

Q11 What is your view on the following measures to ensure security of supply of medicines in the EU?

To establish incentives to counteract the trend in pharma companies to focus on their most recent / most expensive drugs.

Q12 What is your opinion of the following measures to ensure manufacturing and distribution of high quality products?

Measure n°4 might not be relevant for every medicine.

For those therapies that can be manufactured by hospitals / blood banks ... mostly in the public sector, how do we link the absolute necessity to continuously improve on the quality of manufactured therapies, and the obligation of the public health sector to allocate the appropriate resource to comply with these requirements, where there are only cost-recovery systems, rather than a per-product payment ?

Q13 How would you assess the following measures to ensure that the environmental challenges emerging from human medicines are addressed?

- To explore how point-of-care manufacturing and local manufacturing could alleviate the environmental burden of drug manufacturing
- To explore the possibilities for penalties associated with overseas manufacturing

Q14 Is there anything else you would like to add that has not been covered in this consultation?

- Legal basis should be both articles 114 and 168§4 c) TFUE. Therefore, the pharmaceutical legislation should be more balanced in its objectives, especially to take into account the achievement of public health objectives through patients' access to medicines wider, i.e. including those which are not following the standard marketing authorisation pathway or manufactured at the industrial scale.
- The specificities of the rules applicable to different kinds of biological medicinal products should be clarified: current dispersion within the EU legislation, potential overlapping between medicinal products based on recombinant DNA technology and immunological medicinal products.

- The development and need of regulatory support for more coordination at the EU level for bioproduction regarding biotherapies and health data's registries regarding real-world evidence should be taken into account.
- The cumulative implementation of several legislations should be considered: ATMPs and Orphan medicines regulations, GMOs and medicines legislations, medical devices and medicines legislations.